

The French Left's Territorial Standardisation. A Socio-Geographical Analysis of Left-Wing Candidates' Results in the 2022 French Presidential Election

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Abstract

In the 2022 French presidential election, Jean-Luc Mélenchon secured a majority of all left-wing votes across every French constituency — a historic first that comes after decades of declining socialist and communist local anchorage. This paper investigates whether the concept of electoral strongholds still holds relevance when analysing the French left.

By examining the constituency-level results of progressive candidates (Arthaud, Poutou, Mélenchon, Roussel, Jadot, and Hidalgo), we found that their vote distribution was remarkably consistent nationwide. Although the total left-wing vote varied significantly between constituencies, the internal dynamics showed little variation: only twenty out of France's 577 electoral districts exhibited a markedly divergent vote distribution, with Mélenchon obtaining a greater share of left-wing votes in his most sociologically favourable overseas and suburban constituencies. None of the other candidates succeeded in reversing the nationwide vote distribution within any limited set of constituencies, even in their parties' traditional strongholds. This finding undermines the resilience of French left-wing parties, as an unfavourable electoral cycle could potentially eradicate their presence from the political landscape.

Keywords: Electoral sociology, Electoral strongholds, French politics, La France Insoumise, Parti Socialiste, Parti Communiste Français

1. Main text

In 2022, the French left failed to qualify for the presidential election run-off.

Several attempts to explain this defeat quickly emerged in the public debate. One is that too few left-wing votes were strategically given to Mélenchon. Without going back over the substance of this theory, the left would, indeed, have qualified for the run-off had it been less divided. In this context, we wanted to understand who are those who remained in their corridors and why they did so.

Exit polls provided a socio-economic interpretation. All these surveys agreed on the highly variable performance of Jean-Luc Mélenchon among left-wing electorates. LFI's candidate received 80% of all votes cast for left-of-centre candidates by 18–24-year-olds, but less than half among voters aged 70 and over (Ipsos); he received 85% of left-wing votes among people who see themselves as “poor” or “disadvantaged”, but barely 60% among the most affluent (Ifop).

When it comes to electoral studies, however, socio-economics can hardly be the only analysis grid. Other variables, such as perceived political competence, accessibility of polling stations or interpersonal ties, are often stronger determinants of voting patterns than social categories.

In this respect, we attempted to examine presidential candidates' local presence. Given its electoral system (first-past-the-post, single-member constituencies) and its history of mass parties, France is generally considered a country of electoral strongholds (Dubasque & Kocher-Marboeuf, 2014). This factor, which cuts across several of the variables mentioned above, plays an under-estimated role in the French political debate — even for nationwide elections: some consider the Socialist Party's local establishment a key factor in François Mitterrand's first presidential victory, in 1981 (Cagé & Piketty, 2023).

Unlike its socialist, communist, and green counterparts, la France Insoumise is not (and has not sought to become) a party of local fiefdoms. The movement does not compete in most infranational elections and has few local representatives; approximately one-third of its candidates in the 2022 parliamentary election were carpetbagged (Carriat, 2022). LFI also operates on an “occasional militancy” model, which enables mass mobilization during nationwide campaigns but is not conducive to establishing permanent local activities (Cervera-Marzal, 2021). Could the votes that Jean-Luc Mélenchon has missed to qualify for the run-off come from this lack of local presence — if not from rival strongholds?

1.1. Mélenchon's localized dominance in its most sociologically favourable constituencies

We first wanted to find out whether left-wing electorates were, in some territories, proportionally more favourable or unfavourable to Jean-Luc Mélenchon than the national average.

To achieve this, we put into perspective, for each constituency, the share of votes cast for Jean-Luc Mélenchon (FI) with the cumulative share of votes cast for other left-of-centre candidates—i.e. Anne Hidalgo (PS), Yannick Jadot (EELV), Fabien Roussel (PCF), Philippe Poutou (NPA), and Nathalie Arthaud (LO).

Fig. 1. Compared scores of Jean-Luc Mélenchon and the other left-wing candidates in the 2022 French presidential election, by constituency.

Two main trends can be noted.

Firstly, around thirty constituencies saw Jean-Luc Mélenchon win 50% of the votes or more (compared with 21.95% nationwide). In these territories, the non-Melenchonist left's score varied widely but was generally low: less than 8% in most of them, compared with 9.99% nationally. These constituencies, we found, are almost systematically located in Île-de-France and overseas territories. They are urban, much younger and poorer than the national average. Although ethnic statistics are forbidden in France, a higher proportion of non-white voters can also be assumed. They are much more volatile electorally than the rest of the country and often have some of the highest abstention rates.

The strong concentration of these constituencies' left-of-centre electorates in favour of Mélenchon can be explained by several factors. Firstly, the left-wing (as opposed to centre-left) political offer is generally more popular among young, poor, and non-white people. It probably also helped that LFI's election campaign was much more targeted at these socio-demographic categories than other left-of-centre campaigns (NPA being an exception). These groups may also have had greater recourse to a self-protective sort of strategic voting, being the most threatened by both Le Pen's xenophobia and Macron's neoliberalism. Urban areas also tend to accentuate left-of-centre electoral momentum in Europe since it is easier to organise large-scale canvassing and there is greater social pressure to vote.

However, we do not think labelling these places as “FI strongholds” is appropriate. The movement still lacks a strong, permanent establishment there, either in terms of activists (Action Populaire does not underline any sustained post-electoral activity increase) or local elected representatives (LFI failed to win any seat in the indirect 2023 senate elections despite great shares of non-affiliated left-of-centre voters). Little bridges have been built between the party and local political and social structures since the election. Additionally, we still have no guarantee regarding these voters' loyalty – our only indicator so far, European election surveys, let us guess that LFI's domination will shrink.

1.2. Elsewhere, an extreme stability of left-wing progressive patterns

Apart from these few areas, the chart shows a relatively strong correlation ($r = 0.48$) between LFI's vote share and that of other left-of-centre candidates. In other words, a stronger Mélenchon generally goes hand in hand with a stronger score for other left-of-centre candidates (and vice versa).

There do not appear to be “anti-Mélenchon constituencies” where other left-of-centre candidates would have obtained a significantly greater share of left-of-centre votes than the rest of the country. As we can see below, their mean, median, and quartile cumulated scores are both stable and very close together across the country.

Table 1. Minimum, maximum, quartile, mean, and median cumulated vote share of non-LFI left-of-centre candidates as a proportion of the total left-of-centre vote in the 2022 French presidential election, by constituency (distributed by former French regions)

Region (pre-2016 borders)	Minimum	Q1	Median	Mean	Q2	Maximum
Nationwide	6,5	29,0	33,4	31,6	36,8	48,4
Alsace	22,0	27,4	37,1	34,2	39,6	43,0
Aquitaine	28,7	33,8	35,4	35,6	37,8	42,9
Auvergne	31,3	37,0	38,0	37,8	39,2	42,0
Britanny	32,9	37,2	38,3	38,1	39,1	42,0
Burgundy	30,2	32,9	35,4	34,8	36,6	39,4
Centre-Val de Loire	23,0	33,3	35,1	34,4	36,6	38,1
Champagne-Ardennes	29,0	32,3	34,2	33,8	35,5	38,0
Corsica	36,3	37,9	39,4	39,2	40,7	41,5
Franche-Comté	27,3	32,2	33,1	33,3	34,5	40,4
Île-de-France	7,7	20,8	26,7	27,5	31,2	38,5
Languedoc-Roussillon	19,9	28,6	30,4	30,2	32,7	34,3
Limousin	34,3	35,3	36,8	36,6	37,6	39,0
Lorraine	20,2	30,5	33,7	32,6	36,2	38,4
Lower Normandy	31,7	35,8	37,9	37,3	38,7	40,2
Midi-Pyrénées	25,5	31,0	33,0	32,7	34,7	37,5
Nord-Pas-de-Calais	13,7	28,7	35,4	33,1	37,0	48,4
Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur	8,0	27,6	31,0	29,8	33,1	36,9
Pays de la Loire	31,9	36,9	39,2	38,5	40,3	43,4
Picardy	20,8	30,0	32,2	31,4	33,7	38,1
Poitou-Charentes	32,3	35,0	36,3	35,9	37,0	38,3
Rhône-Alpes	16,5	30,7	33,8	33,2	36,8	42,0
Upper Normandy	30,8	31,1	32,0	33,3	36,0	36,3
Overseas territories	6,5	12,0	13,5	18,2	18,9	42,5

With the aforementioned exceptions put aside, non-LFI left-of-centre candidates' cumulated vote share is almost always between 30 and 38% - only once does it exceed 44% (48.4%). No region stands out as having a more anti-LFI left-of-centre electorate.

It is surprising, even in a politically centralised country like France, to see so few electoral variations. Even in 2007, when France had a consolidated two-party system and a non-socialist left in tatters, Ségolène Royal failed to secure an absolute majority of left-of-centre votes in each of France's 577 constituencies.

In this respect, we wondered whether the other left-of-centre parties still held any of their traditional strongholds.

1.3. The disappearance of traditional left-wing electoral strongholds

At first sight, there are still socialist, communist, green, and Trotskyist electoral fiefdoms in France:

Table 2. Minimum, maximum, quartile, mean, and median vote shares obtained by left-of-centre candidates as a proportion of the total left-of-centre vote in the 2022 presidential election, by constituency

Candidate	Minimum	Q1	Median	Mean	Q2	Maximum
Arthaud (LO)	1,5	1,2	1,7	1,9	2,5	4,7
Poutou (NPA)	0,8	1,8	2,5	2,5	3,1	6,7
Roussel (PCF)	0,7	5,4	7,2	7,5	9,1	36,8
Jadot (EELV)	1,4	11,4	14,2	14,3	17,6	27,9
Hidalgo (PS)	1,1	4,3	5,6	5,5	6,6	16,9

The French Left's balance of power appears to be, as we guessed, quite uniform across the country. The table above shows the share of left-of-centre votes obtained by non-LFI candidates; their Q3/Q1 ratio is always between 1.4 and 2 – which is marginal for left-of-centre electoral standards.

All these candidates still appear to hold a handful of constituencies with a vote share well above the national average. The Communist Party, for example, obtained almost 37% of the left-wing vote in a constituency, compared with 7-7.5% nationwide. We have seen, however, that Mélenchon's share of left-of-centre votes did not experience a sharp decrease in these constituencies. A potential explanation could be a localized concentration of the “non-Mélenchon” left-of-centre vote in favour of the left-of-centre party with the strongest local presence.

Such complementarity of national and local political contexts sometimes occurs in elections with a strongly polarizing dominant candidate. In the 2006 Ecuadorian general election, for instance, the centre-left vote was split between three candidates (Gutiérrez, Roldós Aguilera, and Viteri) who all opposed the more radical Rafael Correa. None of them managed to establish themselves as the dominant centre-left alternative as they all obtained 10-17% of the votes, far from the run-off. However, strategic voting mechanisms did indeed take place at the local scale, with each of them seizing up to 75% of the non-Correa left-of-centre votes in the provinces where their parties were best established.

A similar trend in the 2022 French presidential election would suggest the existence of an organized left-of-centre, anti-Mélenchon electorate. To test this hypothesis, we compared left-of-centre candidates' scores in the parliamentary constituencies held for at least 15 years by the Socialist Party (13 constituencies) and the Communist Party (4 constituencies). EELV, NPA and LO, who have not held any legislative constituency or mayoralty all over this period, are by default excluded from this analysis.

Fig. 2. Vote share of Anne Hidalgo (PS) relative to the total left-of-centre votes and total votes cast, by constituency.

Fig. 3. Vote share of Fabien Roussel (PCF) relative to the total left-of-centre votes and total votes cast, by constituency. The constituency located in the upper-right corner of the chart is the electoral district he represents as Member of Parliament.

While Socialists and Communists indeed obtained their best scores in some of their respective strongholds, the general trend does not indicate a much higher mean score in their strongholds than in the rest of the country.

Furthermore, the [vote share relative to all left-of-centre votes / total vote share] ratio for these parties is very stable: on this chart, the Pearson coefficient is 0.72 for Anne Hidalgo and 0.86 for Fabien Roussel, which is extremely high. We can, therefore, rule out the hypothesis of an “organized anti-Mélenchon left-of-centre vote” that would have systematically favoured candidates with stronger local presences. Past electoral and political presence does not appear to have played any significant role in most constituencies.

These parties’ failure to ensure differential electoral mobilisation in their strongholds can be linked to three factors.

First, the gradual disintegration of the political and community fabric since the 1960s. A few decades ago, both the PS and PCF had colossal numbers of activists and held under their influence a dense network of sports, arts, leisure, study, and workers associations in their territories. This helped them keep relatively good results even during their most difficult periods. However, these networks have slowly disintegrated and the voluntary sector is now greatly emancipated from party grips.

Second, La France Insoumise’s approach to activism. Unlike PS, PCF and EELV, Mélenchon’s movement bases its activism on the principles of non-membership and episodic contribution. This approach is detrimental to the movement in “off-peak” periods: in 2019, the movement only had around 4,000 active activists (Cervera-Marzal, 2021), fewer than any of the three other parties. This weakness explains LFI’s inability to run in most cities in the 2020 local elections – and, ultimately, to create electoral strongholds. However, the number of activists tends to explode during presidential campaigns, which enabled the movement to crush its rivals during the last campaign, including on their own turfs.

Third, the French political life’s increasing personalization. Outgoing bonuses and individual approval have become much more prominent in determining one’s vote than party labels in French politics. The repeated election of a local representative hardly means their territory is a stronghold for their party anymore, as demonstrated by the decreasing proportion of local mandates’ retention after an incumbent withdrawal.

1.4. Conclusion and discussion

Traditional left-wing parties no longer have “electoral strongholds” where they’d be protected from poor performances by a significant, permanent electoral threshold. Such a territorial standardisation greatly weakens these parties as it means they can be wiped off the map in just a few years, as proven by the Socialist Party’s loss of 89% of its MPs in the 2017 parliamentary elections. Moreover, most party revenues in France rely on public payments, the amount of which depends on their electoral results; such volatility means that French parties no longer have any medium-term financial guarantees, which ultimately limits their investment capacity.

France Insoumise, on the other hand, obtained much higher scores in around thirty constituencies. However, these victories appear to result more from extremely favourable national context and local sociology than from a long-term, electorally reliable local presence. At this stage, nothing suggests that they

successfully established political strongholds in these territories, neither during the 2022 campaign nor ever since.

This territorial neutralization is not a new normal in contemporary politics. In Hénin-Beaumont or Perpignan, the ruling National Rally now obtains scores even higher than in its sociologically most favourable territories; the same goes for both Swedish or Brazilian left-of-centre parties. Such neutralization is specific to the French left. This is particularly alarming since they have, unlike the other side of the spectrum, very few foreign models to put forward as examples. It is certainly doomed to failure if it also fails to draw on its thousands of local experiences to convince voters of its political project's relevance.

References

- Buton, F., Lemerrier, C., Mariot, N., 2018. « La maisonnée fait la participation : une analyse des itinéraires de participation électorale dans un bureau de vote francilien (1982-2008) », in Cayouette-Remblière, J., Geay, B., Lehingue, P., 2018. *Comprendre le social dans la durée : les études longitudinales en sciences sociales*. Presses Universitaires de Rennes.
- Cagé, J., Piketty, T., 2023. *Une histoire du conflit politique*. Éco-Histoires.
- Carriat, J., 2022 May 16. « Élections législatives 2022 : l'art du parachutage des « insoumis » fait grincer des dents », in *Le Monde*.
- Céville, P. (dir.), 2022 April 10. *Présidentielle 2022 – Jour du vote*. IFOP-Fiducial (27-28).
- Cervera-Marzal, M., 2021. *Le populisme de gauche. Sociologie de la France Insoumise*, Sciences Sociales.
- Dubasque, F., Kocher-Marboeuf, E. (dir.), 2014. *Terres d'élections. Les dynamiques de l'ancrage politique, 1750-2009*. Presses Universitaires de Rennes.
- INSEE, 2022 May 4. Portraits des circonscriptions législatives. Indicateurs économiques et sociodémographiques. Available at <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/6436478>.
- Ministère de l'Intérieur et des Outre-Mer, 2022 April 14. Élection présidentielle des 10 et 24 avril 2022 – Résultats définitifs du 1^{er} tour. Available at <https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/election-presidentielle-des-10-et-24-avril-2022-resultats-definitifs-du-1er-tour>.
- Teinturier, B. (dir.), 2022 April 10. Élection présidentielle 2022. Sociologie des électors et profil des abstentionnistes. Ipsos (16).